

Hand sanitation during COVID 19 Could effective to reduce the gastrointestinal infections in India

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Brief Idea:

We all know that during COVID19 pandemic (1) we followed the safety guidelines and washed our hands properly with soap or any alcohol based sanitizer to prevent COVID 19 viral infection (2). COVID 19 pandemic created more cautiousness in terms of hand hygiene than we were previous. Scholarly articles already discussed the relation between hygiene and infection (3-5). It was reported that hand hygiene is effective in preventing gastrointestinal illnesses both developed and lesser-developed countries (3). Those who had never follows the hand hygiene (for home and street food), they are now maybe habituated and started to keep their hand hygiene. This may have impacted positively also against gastrointestinal infections. Possibility is that it may decreases the Infections (gastrointestinal specifically). But there is lacking of data and good survey based research. So, one can think of it. During statistical analysis researchers have to consider the COVID19 related gastrointestinal complications also.

Declaration: *No conflict of Interest. This is not any research or review article. This is a personal view.*

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